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DATA ANALYTICS SERVICES KITS FOR CONVERTING HEALTHCARE DATA INTO ACTIONABLE INSIGHTS – SCIENCESOFT A CASE STUDY

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Abstract

Big Data Analytics in many fields has brought revolutionary changes. The areas of application such as banking, education, manufacturing, farming, government, transport, media and entertainment are the ones that make extensive use of Big Data Analytics. Healthcare is the one due to Big Data Analytics that has experienced drastic changes. Due to the positive effects of big data, risky jobs like diagnosis, reporting, CRM, predicting the deceases, tracking medical records have become much easier these days. ScienceSoft is an IT company providing information technology services in emerging areas such as CRM, Data Analytics, Collaboration, Knowledge Management, Information Security, etc. ScienceSoft's headquarters is located in McKinney, USA. Organizations such as IBM, Microsoft, Oracle, etc. are collaborating with ScienceSoft due to the reliable and high-quality services provided. This paper attempts to give a broader outlook of Big Data, analyzes the company's business models for handling Big Data Analytics related projects, particularly in the healthcare sector. This paper also contains information related to the challenges of analyzing Big Data, the Company's technologies and tools used in the development of Big Data Analytics projects and how Big Data is converted into useful information to deliver better results in different healthcare related fields.

Keywords: ScienceSoft, Big Data, Data Analytics, CRM, Healthcare Data, EHR, Data Analyzing Tools.

1. INTRODUCTION:

ScienceSoft, an US based IT company established in the year 1989. It is a prominent company that provides solutions in the field of IT, Telecommunication, Transportation, Data Governance, Machine Learning, IoT, Cyber Security services and many more. In Big Data Analytics (BDA), it has been providing customized solutions from the past 14 years. Big Data Analytics will be combined with promising technologies such as the IoT, Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Augmented Reality and Computer Vision to meet the needs of hundreds of customers. This case study uses BDA to disclose the company's services in the healthcare sector. [1-3]. This paper highlights the objective of the study, overview of the concept, its applications, role of ScienceSoft as a BDA Service Provider, companies

contribution in Healthcare, techniques used to analyze Big Data, challenges in BDA and tools used in BDA.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The case study to identify the products that ScienceSoft has developed to convert Big Data into useful information. This study is carried out using the information gathered from the website of the company, relevant information from other online documents [1-5]. The objectives are :

- To get a broader view of BDA
- To know different BDA applications
- To understand more about BDA in Healthcare
- To study the services provided by ScienceSoft in healthcare
- To learn the BDA challenges
- To learn about the tools used in BDA

3. OVERVIEW OF BIG DATA ANALYTICS

BDA is a complex method of exploring big datasets to reveal hidden patterns or unknown relationships, the analysis of which will enable an organization in the decision making process. In many fields of information technology, it has brought revolutionary changes. Big Data contains datasets that are of type audio, video, text, customer transactions, activity logs of users on the social networking sites etc. The collected data must be analyzed using algorithms and converted to the required information that can be used for further analysis in order to reach a conclusion or make a decision. The real challenge is to extract the meaningful information from the ocean of data [6-7].

Properties Big Data

Figure-1 : Properties of Big Data

- **Volume:** Big Data's main feature is the vast amount of data obtained from different sources. The collected data will be in or even more of Tera Bytes. Companies such as Amazon and Facebook generate huge amounts of data. Every customer log creates data and every activity by the user on the social networking site creates data which needs to be captured for analysis[6].

- **Velocity:** In this era of automation, it is not always necessary to feed the required data manually. Data loads are created automatically or at a faster rate with less human interference. Moreover, this data blizzard needs to be quickly stored and processed. Velocity refers to the speed at which the Big Data Analysis system collects, stores and processes the data [6-7].
- **Variety:** By fact, the information collected from different sources will always be unstructured. There will be a wide variety of data collected from various resources. The data will also be in various forms, such as a file or a map or a text message. [6].
- **Veracity:** There is no guarantee that all the data collected will be sufficiently good for processing. Fair, bad, and dirty information will be available. The quality of the data collected depends on the validity or authenticity of the sources. [6].
- **Value:** In order to store and process the massive amount of od information being collected, major investment is needed. There must be some way of turning data volumes into useful information that will add some value to the decision-making process. [6].

4. APPLICATIONS OF BIG DATA ANALYTICS

BDA is used in multiple fields. There are many areas that use Big Data Analytics extensively. Some of them are listed below:

- **Customer Tracking:** Through internet consumer transaction generates information that will be useful in assessing the needs, tastes and desires of the customer. The data collected in this way will be used to design products based on customer needs [8][9].
- **Predictive Analytics:** Complex statistical algorithms and techniques of machine learning are used on the basis of historical data to predict future events. This evaluation will help organizations in the decision-making process [8].
- **Fraud Detection:** There is a lot of possibility of fraud in the banking sector. By reviewing transaction logs, transactions are made by stakeholders. Such details have become a big scam in making online transactions. Big data analysis can be used for identifying fraud to evaluate anomalies in transactions and to find differences in transactions there..[11].
- **Healthcare:** This is the field where Big Data Analysis is used well. By tracking information such as heartbeats, blood pressure, patient sleep patterns and breathing, the device may predict infections before the person actually has any symptoms of the same [9].
- **Sports:** Sports is another prominent field in which Big Data Analytics is used. Video analysis can be used to recognise players' strengths and weaknesses in a squad and other team players as well as to build winning strategies. Data from wearable devices can be used to monitor players' health and provide them with a diet [9].
- **Education:** A huge amount of student-related data will be helpful for assessing students ' learning disabilities. Big data analytics can also be used to improve learner performance and create tailor-made courses for students [10].

5. SCIENCESOFT AS A BIG DATA ANALYTICS SERVICE PROVIDER

ScienceSoft was founded in 1989 as a software development company. It provides information technology services in various fields such as testing and quality assurance, IT consultancy, data analytics, cyber security and network services. To build quality solutions, it integrates all emerging technologies with BDA. It has been providing services to businesses such as Amazon, eBay, Nestle, etc. since the last 30 years. Customer retention accounts for more than 70 percent of its annual income. IT giants like Microsoft, IBM etc. have become business partners because of their deep roots in the field of CRM and Data Analytics. It is listed on the Silicon Review listing as one of the top ten fastest growing data analytics company. The organization has been offering BDA products for the past 14 years. The main activities of the organization were handled from its McKinney headquarters. Yet at Vantaa, Finland, it has another office. BDA being its core expertise, the company has built several applications in the field of healthcare, banking and financial services and manufacturing [1].

6. HEALTHCARE SERVICES PROVIDED BY SCIENCESOFT

Institutions that provide services in the field of healthcare use big data in every available form to improve the quality of their services. They aim at providing best possible solutions without increasing the cost. When dealing with healthcare data analytics, data is captured from various sources such as patients, physicians, lab reports such as PET scan, MRI scan, CT scan, Blood Reports, Ultra Sound Scans etc. The data so gathered will be unstructured one. It has to be stored and analyzed for the purpose of effective decision making. It must be stored and analyzed for effective decision-making reasons. The company provides services to more than 200 United States healthcare institutions. It has designed solutions available to fulfill the needs of the institutions [11]. Services offered by the company in the field of healthcare include the following:

6.1 Intelligent Healthcare System

Intelligent Healthcare System accepts the data from the patient with the help of a Mobile App. Since the symptoms of every disease are different, every disease requires different mobile apps. The mobile apps handle all communications between the patient and the software.

Entire data related to patient will now be recorded in each patient's Electronic Health Record (EHR), which includes patients' health information in electronic format. Intelligent Healthcare System accepts the data from patients and stores it in HER. Data thus stored is used by the Data Analytics Software to provide clear analysis of patient's present health conditions. The report related to the analysis will be given to doctor in the form of notification and the doctor after going through the analyzed data will notify the patient regarding the treatment with the help of mobile app [12].

Figure-2. Functioning of Intelligent Healthcare System

Figure 2 demonstrates the operation of the Smart System of healthcare. It is used by patients with chronic diseases such as diabetes, asthma, heart problems, behavioral problems, knee joint pain, etc. Patients enter their illness details, food information, disorders such as muscle pain, blood pressure, blood sugar levels and allergies to drugs, if any, with the help of a mobile app. The Intelligent Healthcare System will send all data to the EHR. A centralized data warehouse will be in operation where all the data will be stored. The algorithms for data analytics use the information stored in the EHR to determine the patient's present situation. This analyzed information is given to the doctor in the form of notifications that further analyze the patient's information and send the patient personalized information. Using the mobile app, the patient must read the doctor's recommendations. The customized knowledge will include medication to be taken, the food to be eaten and avoided, the physical activities to be carried out and to be avoided, the schedule of appointments and the details of lab reports.

Advantages

- It saves lot of time.
- Upto date information about the patient will be available
- There will be continuous monitoring of patients
- Scheduling of appointments is easy as the doctor knows the current situation of the patient
- Quality of service provided to the patients is improved
- Patient can access his data any time
- Customer (patient) satisfaction is improved

Disadvantages

- There will be security and privacy issues related to patient's data. To overcome these issues, the records are stored and handled by authorized third party.
- Accessing the information related to a patient by himself will create unnecessary tension.
- Records must be updated after receiving input from patients and after their every visit to the hospital and laboratories otherwise it will lead to inaccurate results [13].

6.2 Image Analysis in Medical Sciences

Analysis of the image is very much necessary in medical science. The study of images is a multidisciplinary field involving complex algorithms, physics, mathematics and many more. It includes X-Rays analysis, the examination of CT Scan reports, MRI Scan reports, PET scan reports, Ultra-Sound Scanning reports, etc. have become an essential part of medical diagnosis. The photos will be in different format created by each medical device. In the data warehouse, the images obtained from different instruments are recorded and data analytics algorithms are developed to obtain accurate results. In short, this is used to detect the exact location of tumors in the brain and cancer cells. Medical image analysis program uses

- **Software** to improve the captured image quality. If the captured image is not of the required quality, computer algorithms are used to generate clear image from the existing one.
- **Segmentation** methods for determining the exact area and separating infected cells from non-infected cells. This will help to prevent damage to healthy cells that is very important in the diagnosis of brain cancer.
- **Machine learning** algorithms are used for the diagnosis so that the disease is diagnosed at earlier stage. This will enhance the survival rate of the patients.

Medical Image Analysis is used to diagnose accurately abdominal diseases, brain tumors, spinal cord related diseases, diseases related to mammary glands, respiratory organs and kidneys

6.3 Cancer Drug Manufacturing System

ScienceSoft is providing smart solutions to a multi-national company that manufactures generic and non-generic cancer drugs that are used in chemotherapy. The shelf-life of these drugs will be very short hence they require smart manufacturing so as to avoid over-stock and out of stock situations. In most of the situations the medicines used in chemotherapy are combinations of several drugs. The dosage and the combination varies from patient to patient. ScienceSoft implemented the solution by making use of .NET framework. Hospitals and Drug houses use the software to place their orders. The order information is stored in databases for the further analysis. As per the order, the customized drug is manufactured and supplied to the patient. At any time, the patient can track their order.

This system is used to maintain the stock of drugs, the stock of chemical compounds used to manufacture those drugs, update inventories and automate billing and payment processes. In addition to this, the software will generate different types of reports such as hospital reports, patients' report, drug report, stock reports etc. BDA algorithms are used in manufacturing process to reduce the wastage of medicines because of excess stock [15].

6.4 Other Useful Health care Applications

ScienceSoft has created a series of Android Apps for engaging patients, educating patients on health and hygiene, fitness tracking systems, medication reminders, addiction tracking systems, mindfulness and relaxation systems. Smart devices such as blood pressure monitors, thermometers, sleep monitors, heart rate monitors, etc. can easily integrate these apps in order to provide better care for the needy. They inhibit two-way communication between patients and their caregivers. To provide up-to-date patient-related information, all patient mobile apps and smart devices need to be connected to EHR[8].

7. TECHNIQUES USED TO ANALYZE BIG DATA

The analysis of big data requires sophisticated techniques to analyze huge amounts of data. There are several techniques that can be used to make simple knowledge from voluminous data.

They are to be selected depending on the type of application [16]. Some of them include:

- **Association rule mining:** This approach is used in case of large datasets to find the hidden relationship between two or more variables. It is commonly used in supermarkets to know the relationships between buying different items.
- **Classification tree analysis:** This technique is used for categorizing the data. It requires prior information and knowledge of problem. It is used to automatically categorize the documents. It is commonly used in the disciplines of healthcare.
- **Genetic algorithms:** Using this approach, the features of two or more things are combined to form a new one with better features. It is widely used to build new products from existing ones. It includes two operations- mutation and crossover.
- **Machine learning:** This is an Artificial Intelligence technique which requires large number of training sets. Without the aid of explicit software, computers learn automatically in machine learning. It is commonly used to assess the disorder in health.
- **Regression analysis:** In this technique, some independent variables are manipulated to see the influence on some other variables. It is most efficient technique to deal with quantitative data. It is used in business, real estate, weather forecasting etc.
- **Sentiment analysis:** It involves the analysis of feelings of patients, feelings of customers and opinions of public. It is used widely in healthcare and hospitality sciences. This method is also used in analyzing the behavior and feedback of customers for making improvements in hotel and hospitality industries.
- **Social network analysis:** It is the analysis of interpersonal relationships for commercial reason. This is a popular technique applied in the analysis of security applications, internet applications etc to find out the correlation between two or more variables.

8. CHALLENGES IN BIG DATA ANALYTICS

In this digital age, enormous amount of records are generated every minute. Each online transaction by every individual, every reading on the EHR in case of healthcare creates data of some use. This has to be captured and analyzed for decision making[9][17]. Few challenges faced in handling of big data include

- **Information from diverse sources:** Healthcare data analytics requires data to be collected from various sources such as X-Ray images, ECGs, Ultra-Sound Scanning, medical reports etc. Since they are from different sources, they will be definitely in distinct format. Storing the data from diverse sources is the biggest challenge. Different formats of data will definitely make it a tough job for selecting proper attributes so that it can be stored properly.
- **Shortage of experts:** BDA demands voluminous data which is to be accessed and processed periodically. It requires use of complex algorithms and tools. This field has created ample job opportunities but still the industry is facing a shortage of experts.

- **Selecting appropriate format and data:** As data is gathered in different sources, it will obviously there in different format. Selecting the proper data becomes a challenge as there will be useful data, noise and inconsistent data. Selecting only meaningful data and processing it is very important in BDA.
- **Storage and backup for the data:** As the data grows exponentially, selecting the right storage medium is very important factor because the proper storage medium has high impact on time required for the retrieval of required data.
- **Security issues:** Voluminous data needs to be protected properly. Safeguarding the sensitive information is the most challenging task of BDA. There will be difficulty in recovery of massive amount of data if lost due to lack of proper security measures.
- **Data visualization techniques:** By using data visualization tools,

9. TOOLS USED IN BIG DATA ANALYTICS

BDA tools are nothing but softwares which are used in the analysis of large amount of data for providing required knowledge. They are widely used for large amounts of data visualization. There are a range of products in the market [19][20]. Some of them include:

- **Apache Hadoop:** It is an open-source framework that is widely used in BDA by the companies that provide services in this field. It is used for research and development considerations.
- **CDH(Cloudera Distribution for Hadoop):** This is an open-source and easy to use tool. It provides higher security for the data.
- **MongoDB:** It is NoSQL document oriented system. It is an open-source software tool that can be installed on different platforms such as Windows, Linux, Solaris and FreeBSD. It is easy to learn, cost effective and reliable. These features made it popular in the field of data analytics.
- **R Programming:** This tool is used extensively for statistical analysis. It is open source, multi-paradigm and is dynamic in nature and is broadly used for the purpose of data visualization.
- **Apache SAMOA:** This tool is suitable for machine learning. It provides different algorithms that can be used in case of data mining and machine learning for the purpose of analysis.
- **Lumify:** This tool is used for data visualization. It provides 2D and 3D graphs. It is widely used in healthcare data analysis and association rule mining.
- **Talend:** This is an easy-to-use tool which automates the integration of different types of data. It is used extensively in machine learning and natural language processing.
- **Skytree:** It is mainly used for artificial intelligence and data science applications. It is a software that offers GUI functionality which makes it easy to use.

10. CONCLUSION

BDA has the potential to transform the way healthcare providers use advanced tools to gain insight into their medical and other information sources and to make informed choices. We will see the rapid, widespread adoption and use of BDA throughout the healthcare sector and the healthcare industry in the future. As BDA becomes more prevalent, topics such as

protecting the confidentiality, safeguarding security, setting standards and governance, and continually improving tools and technologies will attract attention. BDA and healthcare applications are at a nascent stage of development, but rapid technology and software developments will accelerate their maturing phase. In this context, due to the two-way contact between patients and their care providers, the solutions proposed by ScienceSoft enhance customer satisfaction. These software in turn make the life of patients more easy.

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